
Staff Notice SN 57/23

Safeguarding Policy

March 2023

Safeguarding Policy

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1. Introduction

PML has a fundamental responsibility to provide an environment in which individuals of all ages, whether employees, students or visitors, may work, learn and develop safely. This responsibility includes an ethical and moral duty to safeguard children and adults at risk at any time when they are engaging with PML staff, students, volunteers and contractors in PML-led activities, whether on or off PML premises, including activities at sea.

This is at the heart of PML’s interaction with the wider community both within the UK and overseas, and acknowledges that in all interactions with children and adults at risk, their welfare is of paramount importance.

PML’s [Core Values](#) include “responsibility”, “integrity” and “respect” and the relevance of these to this policy is outlined below:

- **Responsibility:** Employees are expected to act for the betterment of people, including our staff, and the environment on local to global scales. This includes taking responsibility for their behaviour and a shared responsibility for challenging or addressing inappropriate behaviour that could put individuals at risk;
- **Integrity:** Employees are expected to act with professional and appropriate behaviour at all times;

- **Respect:** Employees are expected to show consideration and thoughtfulness in relation to staff, funders/customers, partners, civil society and the environment. This underpins the way employees and students can expect to be treated and mechanisms for raising concerns.

2. Purpose of the document

This document provides information in relation to:

- The definition of child and adult at risk;
- Understanding roles and responsibilities in relation to safeguarding;
- How a safeguarding concern should be raised;
- What will happen when a concern is raised.

3. Scope of the document

This document applies to all PML, UKRI/NERC and PML Applications Ltd employees, students and visitors engaging in PML Group (PML and/or PML Applications) led activities and engaging with children or adults at risk.

For the purposes of this document:

“Child/children” refers to anyone under the age of 18 years.

“Adult at risk” refers to someone who is over the age of 18 years who has (a) care and support needs and (b) is experiencing, or is at risk of, neglect or physical, mental or emotional harm; and (c) as a result of those needs is unable to protect themselves against neglect or harm, or the risk of it.

It is recognised that the level of engagement with children and adults at risk is limited within the PML Group. Employment and opportunities for work experience are only available for those under 18 years where they are part of a PML wide, organised event, subject to a safeguarding risk assessment and appropriate DBS checks. Other examples where employees may be working with children or adults at risk may include responsibilities for outreach activities within school settings; working overseas in local, vulnerable communities; or supervising a PhD student or employee who has a disability or physical / mental health condition that means they are unable to protect themselves from significant harm or exploitation.

Subsequent reference in the document to “employees” is intended to include students, and where applicable, visitors.

4. Types of abuse

Abuse can include:

- **physical abuse** such as hitting, slapping or pushing;
- **neglect** such as not being cared for properly, ignoring medical or physical needs, not having enough food, water or heating;
- **emotional or psychological abuse** such as shouting or swearing, threats or intimidation, not being allowed to see friends and family or make their own choices;
- **sexual abuse** such as unwanted touching, kissing, sexual intercourse or sexual contact without consent or with pressured consent;
- **financial abuse** such as theft, forcing someone to sign over money or property, making financial transactions without consent;
- **discriminatory abuse** such as comments about someone's disability, age, illness or sexual orientation;
- **domestic abuse** such as controlling, forceful or threatening behaviour, honour-based violence and female genital mutilation;
- **modern slavery** such as human trafficking and forced labour.

5. Responsibilities

5.1 PML Board of Trustees & PML Applications' Board of Directors

The PML Board of Trustees and PML Applications Board of Directors are responsible for ensuring that policies are in place to enable PML or PML Applications, respectively, to meet its statutory obligations. The PML Board has a responsibility to report any serious incidents to the Charity Commission.

Where an incident involves a member of the SMT, the Member of the Board with designated Safeguarding responsibilities, Chair of RemCo, will carry out an investigation, supported where necessary by an external advisor.

5.2 Chief Executive, PML and PML Applications Ltd

The Chief Executive is responsible for ensuring members of the PML Group community are able to report safeguarding concerns and that designated safeguarding officers are in place with the knowledge and skills to take appropriate action to protect children and adults at risk.

5.3 Head of People & Culture / Head of Postgraduate Studies

The Head of People & Culture and Head of Postgraduate Studies are designated safeguarding officers, with responsibility for ensuring the Safeguarding Policy is fit for purpose. Responsibilities include identifying relevant roles where people will work with children and adults and risk, ensuring DBS checks are undertaken at the appointment stage, maintaining records and reporting safeguarding concerns to the appropriate authority where applicable and carrying out investigations and disciplinary action where inappropriate behaviour is identified.

5.4 Employees

Employees are expected to treat everyone with respect and take responsibility to ensure their actions and behaviours are consistent with the high levels of integrity and trust expected by PML Group. In addition, there is an expectation for all members of PML Group to report concerns where they observe inappropriate behaviour carried out by colleagues when on PML Group business.

Employees are responsible for reporting any concerns they become aware of where children or adults at risk are being abused or mistreated. Concerns must be reported to the Head of People & Culture or Postgraduate Studies.

Employees should feel able to report concerns without fear of retribution or disadvantage, as outlined in PML's [Whistleblowing \(Public Interest Disclosure\) Policy](#).

This procedure is **not** for employees to raise concerns in relation to bullying or harassment unless the individual who is subject to the inappropriate behaviour is a child or adult at risk. In other instances of inappropriate behaviour that constitutes bullying and harassment, employees should refer to the [Respect at Work](#) guidance.

5.5 PhD Supervisors

PhD Supervisors should ensure they are familiar with both this Safeguarding Policy, and relevant policies within the University the student is registered with. Supervisors should report any safeguarding concerns to the Head of Postgraduate Studies.

6. At a glance - flowchart

7. Procedure for reporting a safeguarding incident

7.1 Reporting

Should any member of PML become aware of a safeguarding issue, they first need to carry out a dynamic assessment of the situation to check that the child or adult at risk is safe. For any child or adult at risk in imminent danger, they should call 999 immediately.

If the child or adult at risk is not in imminent danger, the individual should check that they have access to appropriate support or signposting to professional services as appropriate.

The individual should check contact details and advise the child or adult at risk that because of concerns for their welfare, they will be making a safeguarding report to one of PML's designated safeguarding officers.

The individual should complete the report form in the appendix of this policy and email it to Head of People & Culture or Head of Postgraduate Studies.

7.2 Action

The Head of People & Culture or Head of Postgraduate Studies will check what action, if any has been taken. They will determine what additional information is required, contact the person who reported the issue or the child or adult at risk to determine whether this constitutes a safeguarding concern, and where appropriate, notify the relevant statutory body as appropriate.

Where a significant issue is identified that creates risk to an individual that involves the local authority and/or police, the Head of People & Culture or Head of Postgraduate Studies will refer the incident to the Company Secretary to update the Chair of the Board of Trustees and report the incident to the Charity Commission.

Anonymous reporting of incidents will be made to the Board on an annual basis.

Where any allegations of misconduct arise against a PML employee, an investigation will be carried out and subsequent disciplinary action where appropriate. Depending on the seriousness of allegations, suspension may be considered. Please refer to PML's [Disciplinary Policy](#).

7.3. Confidentiality

All disclosures under this policy and associated personal information will be treated in a sensitive manner and kept secure within PML, passed on only to authorised designated individuals with responsibilities for safeguarding.

PML has a statutory duty to report safeguarding issues to the relevant authority and advise the child or adult at risk where a disclosure needs to be made and cannot therefore commit to maintaining confidentiality where an individual is at risk.

8. Children and adults at risk in the workplace

Safeguarding also involves ensuring the health and safety of children and adults at risk whilst conducting or taking part in PML Group activities. It is a legal requirement under the Management of Health and Safety at

Work Regulations (1999) that all activities involving young persons (under the age of 18) and vulnerable staff are risk assessed. This means that all relevant risk assessments must be reviewed to take into account the enhanced risk that may be incurred due to the involvement of a less experienced or vulnerable individual.

Risk assessments must consider the following factors;

- Whether the work requires a certain physical or psychological capacity beyond their capacity
- Whether the work involves harmful chemicals, biological hazards or radiation to which they may be more vulnerable
- Whether their lack of experience in a work place setting may increase the risk of accident/incident occurring.
- The effect of a lack of knowledge and training
- The effect of reduced or less well developed communication skills which may prevent understanding hazard warnings
- Children and adults at risk may not have the confidence to admit when an activity is beyond their capability.

In the case of young persons, regulation 10 of the legislation requires such risk assessments to be shared with those who have parental responsibility. This will be led by PML Human Resources.

9. Support, Information and Advice

PML offers a 24/7 helpline through [CareFirst](#) that can provide information, advice and guidance, including access to support and counselling.

Information and support can be accessed through [PML Welfare Officers](#), Human Resources or Head of Postgraduate Studies.

For further information relating to the legal framework and government guidance, please refer to:

- [The Health and Safety at Work Act 1974](#)
- [The Rehabilitation of Offenders Act 1974](#)
- [Sexual Offences Act 2003](#)
- [The Safeguarding Vulnerable Groups Act 2006](#)
- [Disclosure and Barring Service \(DBS\)](#)
- [Keeping Children Safe in Education](#)
- [Children and Young People in the Workplace \(Health and Safety Executive\)](#)

Safeguarding Policy	Changes highlighted in blue
This Version	2
Policy owner	Head of People & Culture
SMT Review	21 February 2023
Board sign off	23 March 2023

Human Resources Group

March 2023

Safeguarding reporting form

Your name (person reporting the incident):

Your contact details: Telephone:; Email:

What are you reporting?

I am concerned about a child or adult at risk	
I was witness to an incident with a child or Adult at Risk	
I was involved in an incident with a child or Adult at Risk	
A child or Adult at Risk has told me they are being abused	
I have received an allegation of abuse	

Key information about the child or Adult at Risk where known

Name of child or Adult at Risk concerned	
Contact details (phone/email)	
Date of birth	
Your role in relating to the child or Adult at Risk	
Please confirm whether the child or Adult at Risk is aware of this report	

Please describe the incident or concern. Only report what you know, do not ask the individual for personal information. For example please report: what the vulnerable person has told you, any observation you have made in terms of signs of distress, inappropriate relationships, a change in attitude, behaviour or appearance.

Please describe any action that has been taken

Any other comments

Your signature: **Date:**

Privacy notice. The information collected on this form will be used solely to support PML’s Safeguarding Policy.

Please send this to either juda@pml.ac.uk where this relates to an employee or visitor, or ruai@pml.ac.uk where this relates to a student.